

The Need to Increase Funding for Research and Innovation

Europe wants to support the growth of its economies and the competitiveness of its businesses, as well as to contribute to human prosperity and development. It also needs to address a variety of local and global challenges. To do these things, Europe must maintain its capacity to produce and use knowledge through science, research, and innovation. However, it lacks the necessary funding for these activities.

EU Member States Lag Behind in R&D

Over the past decades, the EU has encouraged increased investment in research to stimulate the competitiveness of the EU. Its 'Europe 2020' strategy has the objective of spending 3% of GDP in the EU on research and development activities.

However, actual spending in the Member States lags well behind that objective **and behind most other developed countries**. To complement national and private investment, the EU needs to also increase its own R&D spending.

Source: OECD estimates based on OECD Main Science and Technology Indicators Database, March 2018

EU Member States Lag Behind in Patent Applications

Currently, the EU dramatically lags behind in patent applications, as other regions offer conditions that are more beneficial to innovation and the development of new technologies. Europe needs to support the dynamic interplay between research and innovation.

Source: WIPO, World Intellectual Property Indicators 2017

Under Horizon 2020, out of all the world-class research determined to be 'scientifically excellent'...

Source: Interim Evaluation of Horizon 2020

Three out of four research projects that could have had meaningful and lasting impact were turned down due to lack of funding.

The European Commission had high expectations for Horizon Europe. Increased funding would create extra jobs, generate GDP growth, and drive innovation. Sadly, the actual funding proposed by the European Commission **barely improves on that of Horizon 2020**.

Amount of proposal expressed in 2018 constant prices.

Source of employment and GDP growth estimates: Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council and the Council: A new, modern Multiannual Financial Framework for a European Union that delivers efficiently on its priorities post-2020

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Science Europe is a non-profit organisation based in Brussels representing major Research Funding and Research Performing Organisations across Europe.

More information on its mission and activities is provided at www.scienceeurope.org.

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